

On Schisms and ‘generalism’

A review of Sarosh Anklesaria’s thoughts on future of architecture

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Sarosh Anklesaria, a practicing architect, critic and educator, seems to have a refreshing take on how architects should operate. Refreshing in the very literal sense because what he refers to was once encoded in to the architect’s conduct, having being lost to the *zeitgeist* of the industrial age. He terms it as ‘generalism’, the ability to reach out across wide variety of disciplines and work under them, not unlike the ‘Ideal Architect’ of Vitruvius. Unfortunately, reality is far grimmer. Rarely do we find architects who can think *and* act beyond just the building and rarely enough talking about food security and income parity, which Anklesaria does!

We live in a world where the role of architect is becoming increasingly redundant; less than 3% of the cities are designed by architects, our services are limited to a niche market and with the rise of technology such as A.I. and 3D printers, a creative revolution is more likely. At such a time, the need for architects to adapt, reinvent and broaden their horizons should be driven by selfish needs if nothing else. Also, by limiting the architect to just the building itself and architecture just to the architect, as these *purist architects** do so often, seems to reflect what Anklesaria points out is the idea of the neoliberal system i.e. of mono-use. He, to the horror of *purist architects*, shows us the potential of thinking otherwise. By referring to the inherent potentialities of architecture, the ‘schism’, he talks about tools that architects can deploy to respond to our contexts.

Anklesaria rightly points how the duality of architecture, the interior and exterior, at a glance seem to refer to different areas, the interior addresses syntax and the exterior talks about Environmentalism, but this is precisely where the generalist tendencies come in to play. This schism, of architecture as an object and a subject, is not a hinderance but instead provides the platform to draw upon varied disciplines to resolve the issues of our time. The ability of architecture to fluidly move across various scales and disciplines, from global levels where you can address issues of food-security, to the scale of city where you can develop urban systems and eventually to the individual where you respond to very peculiar needs is its most powerful feature. Fortunately for us, his work shows that ability and that the possibility exists is enough cause for students of architecture to think beyond just the building.

He also raises a pertinent question about the agency of architecture, if architecture possesses the quality to affect the entire spectrum from the global to the individual then what are its

* *Purist architect*: Who believes only buildings constructed by them are architecture and the only job of the architect is to build 500 yd² houses in for the 0.1%

effect, how does it manifest and most importantly where does this agency lie? And again, to the absolute horror of the *purist architects*, Anklesaria implicitly makes it quite clear that the agency of architecture lies with essentially everyone and not just the architect. His proposals for an incremental house in Ahmedabad manifest these tendencies quite visibly. His overall philosophy puts the human back in architecture on the human's *own* terms instead of the architect's. He also refers to '*jugaad*' and 'degrowth' as viable tools for architect, thus allowing us to address the de-humanizing qualities so pervasive in our practice of architecture.

To sum it up, Sarosh Anklesaria, offers us a glimpse in to a different species of architects, sadly alien to our country. What he talks about isn't entirely new, it draws on centuries of wisdom of how architects operated,[†] but he makes sure that they are relevant to our times. One can only hope that this vision for architecture is adopted before Pinterest is shut down and puts us all out of business.

[†] Refer to *The Architect* by Spiro Kostof.